

Introduction of Arsenic into Coumarin Nucleus.

Part I.

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No attempt appears to have hitherto been made to introduce arsenic into coumarin nucleus by any of the general methods, *e.g.*, Bart's reaction (D. R. P. 250264) or Roeder and Blasi's method (*Ber.*, 1914, 47, 2748). In view of the well-known facts that sodium cinnamate and sodium *o*-coumarate (Hetol) augment the number of polymorphonuclear white blood corpuscles and thereby help in checking tuberculosis, and that the group -O-CO- present in many drugs is supposed to be responsible for increasing internal secretions, the combination of the coumarin molecule, which possesses these groupings, with the therapeutically active pentavalent arsenic atom appeared to us to have great potentialities as a drug.

The introduction of arsenic by the method of Roeder and Blasi failed because the coumarin mercuri-chloride was found to be decomposed by arsenic chloride regenerating coumarin. In this connection we wish to record the fact that the coumarin mercuri-chloride required for Roeder and Blasi's reaction, which was prepared from coumarin and mercuric acetate by Dimroth's method (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2154), did not offer any of the peculiar difficulties in its preparation which appear to have been encountered by Sen and Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 847).

The application of Bart's reaction to 6-aminocoumarin, however, led to the formation of an arsenic derivative crystallising from acetic acid as a yellow microcrystalline solid, melting and decomposing at 200°. The analytical figures both for arsenic, carbon and hydrogen are in agreement with those required for tricoumarylarsenic oxide of the formula: $(C_9H_5O_2)_3As:O$.

The compound, like triphenylarsenic oxide and other similar bodies, dissolves in alkalis and alkaline carbonate and is reprecipitated by acids.

As the employment of arsenious oxide and sodium carbonate according to the original Bart's method led to much frothing and the formation of considerable amount of tarry matter, the reaction was modified by using a solution of arsenic trichloride in hydrochloric acid when the reaction proceeded smoothly and gave a good yield (about 55 per cent.) of the product

The compound has been examined for finding out the maximum and minimum lethal doses.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Mercuration of Coumarin.—Coumarin (10 g.), 96 per cent. acetic acid (100 c.c.) and freshly prepared mercuric acetate (12 g.) were taken in a stout flask and heated under pressure in an oil-bath at 140-50° for five hours. After cooling the mixture was filtered and the residue washed with acetic acid. The filtrate and washings were evaporated to a small volume and treated with alcoholic calcium chloride to convert the acetate into the less soluble chloride. This was filtered and the product washed successively with water, hot water, alcohol and ether, the latter solvent being used to remove any unchanged coumarin. The coumarin mercuri-chloride thus obtained was dried in a vacuum desiccator (yield 50 per cent.).

The compound decomposes at 178°. The properties of this compound are identical with those recorded by Sen and Chakravarti. (Found: Hg, 52.01, 51.95. $C_9H_5O_2Cl Hg$ requires Hg, 52.55 per cent.).

Introduction of Arsenic into the Coumarin Nucleus.—The following are some of the attempts to introduce arsenic into the coumarin nucleus *via* coumarin mercuri-chloride:

(a) A mixture of coumarin mercuric-chloride (4 g.) and arsenic trichloride (10 g.) was heated in a pressure flask on a water-bath for 5 hours. The whole was then allowed to settle for two days when crystals of mercuric chloride settled at the bottom and the supernatant liquid consisted of two layers. The upper one was colourless, whilst the lower one was brown. The latter was separated from mercuric chloride and subjected to distillation under reduced pressure. The first fraction collected at 94-95° was reddish in colour which on chlorination and subsequent treatment with water resulted in the dissolution of the oily layer with rise in temperature. The second portion collected between 98° and 105° was similarly

treated and this resulted in the precipitation of a crystalline mass which on examination was found to be arsenious oxide.

(b) A mixture of coumarin mercuri-chloride (5 g.) and arsenic trichloride (17 g.) was heated in absence of air at 140-50° for 4 hours. There were formed two layers and a precipitate of mercuric chloride. Each layer on distillation under reduced pressure followed by chlorination and treatment with water gave no arsenic derivative of coumarin.

(c) A mixture of coumarin mercuri-chloride (11 g.) and arsenic trichloride (35 g.) was heated under reflux over a direct flame for 5 hours and the resulting liquid was allowed to settle overnight. The white precipitate collected at the bottom was separated by filtration through glass wool and the filtrate subjected to vacuum distillation. The fraction collected at 60-62°/17-18 mm., on analysis, was found to be arsenic trichloride. The residue in the distilling flask became pasty. This was treated with ether whereby a small portion went into solution. The ethereal extract on evaporation and treatment with water and chlorine was found to give coumarin. The residue in the flask was mercuric chloride.

(d) Coumarin mercuri-chloride (14 g.) and arsenic trichloride (25 g.) were heated on a water-bath for 4-5 hours and was allowed to stand overnight. The clear solution was next subjected to distillation which began at 140° and continued up to 270°. The distillate on examination was found to be arsenic trichloride and the white residue in the distilling flask nothing but coumarin.

(e) The solution obtained by heating coumarin, mercuric-acetate, and acetic acid was filtered and was treated with arsenic chloride in the cold ; a white precipitate was produced which was washed with cold acetic acid to dissolve mercuric acetate and then with warm water. On examination it was found to be coumarin mercuri-chloride.

Tricoumaryl Arsenic Oxide.—(i) Arsenious oxide (24 g.) was dissolved in sodium carbonate (32 g. in 300 c.c. water) solution with the application of heat ; to this copper sulphate (0.7 g.) was added. The mixture was cooled to 0° in a vessel provided with a mechanical stirrer and to this a diazotised solution of 6-aminocoumarin (15 g. of amino-compound, 20 c.c. hydrochloric acid in 60 c.c. of water and 7 g. of sodium nitrate in 20 c.c. of water) cooled to 0° was gradually added during the course of 1 hour. Vigorous frothing which is usual in such reactions was partially avoided by adding

a little benzene and increasing the speed of rotation of the stirrer. The stirring was continued for one hour after the addition of the diazotised solution. The product was then allowed to stand overnight. The mass was then filtered; the filtrate was evaporated to one third of the original volume, boiled with animal charcoal and filtered again. To the filtrate strong hydrochloric acid was added gradually when most of the tarry matter separated; it was filtered and the filtrate was finally acidified when the tricoumaryl arsenic oxide was precipitated as a dark brown mass. This on being repeatedly crystallised from acetic acid was obtained as a light yellow microcrystalline mass melting with slight decomposition at 200°

(ii) *By Modified Bart's Process.*— 6-Aminocoumarin (10 g.) dissolved in hydrochloric acid (25 c.c. in 40 c.c. of water) was diazotised with a solution of sodium nitrite (4.5 g. in 20 c.c. of water) the temperature being kept near 0° and to this copper sulphate (0.5 g.) was added. In three separate vessels arsenic trichloride (14 g.), water (25 c.c.) and hydrochloric acid (25 c.c.) were taken, each cooled initially to 10° and then mixed together, and the mixture thus obtained was added drop by drop to the well-cooled diazo-solution with stirring. The resulting solution was kept overnight and then filtered. The filtrate, light yellow in colour, was made alkaline with sodium hydroxide solution when a precipitate was formed which redissolved in excess of alkali to a dark brown solution. This was concentrated, boiled with animal charcoal and filtered. The filtrate on being acidified produced a precipitate which was twice crystallised from acetic acid. It was light yellow in colour and its melting point and percentage of arsenic were found to be identical with those of the previous compound obtained by Bart's method. The mixed m.p. was also 200° .

Tricoumaryl arsenic oxide prepared by both the methods is soluble in acetic acid but sparingly soluble in acetone and insoluble in all other organic solvents. It dissolves in ammonia, caustic alkalis and sodium carbonate solution with a reddish-brown colour from which acids precipitate the oxide.

The reaction probably takes the following course:—

(Found: C, 59·87, 59·99 ; H, 3·02 ; As, 13·8, 13·85, 13·9. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_7\text{As}$ requires C, 61·50 ; H, 2·80 ; As, 14·2 per cent.). The estimation of arsenic was carried out by the methods of Norton and Koch (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 27, 1247) and of Ewins (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 1356).

The following toxicological tests were carried out by Mr. P. B. Sen, M. Sc., Lecturer in Biochemistry, Calcutta University, to whom our best thanks are due.

The toxicity of the sodium salt of the compound was determined and was found to be in the normal range as will be evident from the following table. The strength of the solution, which contained 0·85 per cent. of common salt, was 2 per cent.

Amount injected per kg.	Weight of the rat.	Vol. of the solution.	Remarks.
0·04 g.	105 g.	0·21 c.c.	Survived
0·06	95	0·29	"
0·07	55	0·19	"
0·08	91	0·37	"
0·09	96	0·43	"
0·26	110	1·44	"
0·28	85	1·19	"
0·30	84	1·24	"
0·30	126	1·94	"
0·33	126	1·03	"
0·35	100	0·87	"
0·35	135	1·18	"
0·35	60	0·52	Proved fatal †
0·37	90	0·83	" *
0·37	140	1·28	Survived
0·37	145	1·30	Proved fatal *
0·39	30	0·29	"
0·39	30	0·29	"
0·39	35	0·339	"
0·40	43	0·86	"
0·40	85	1·70	" ‡

* After 12 hours.

† After 24 hours.

‡ After 36 hours.

Thus it may be seen that the maximum and minimum lethal doses are comparable to those of soamin and are respectively 0·39 and 0·34 g. The therapeutic activity is being examined by Dr. A. C. Ukil of Indian Research Fund Association.

The investigation is being continued with substituted coumarins and naphthacoumarins.

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